

1 **HSV-1 ICP27 activates Rnf44.**

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6 We measured total transcription in cells expressing doxycycline-inducible ICP27 to describe network
7 interaction partners of the viral gene product. We demonstrate here that a primary transcriptional
8 consequence of ICP27 expression is induction of *Rnf44*.

8 Citations

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